

THE OUTCOME OF PERCEIVED PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT IN NON-PROFIT EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15846875>

Keywords

Performance Management (PM), Work Performance (WP), Organizational Commitment (OC), Turnover Intention (TI), Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), and Job Satisfaction (JS)

Article History

Received: 03 April, 2025

Accepted: 24 June, 2025

Published: 09 July, 2025

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Abstract

This study investigates employees' perceptions of performance management (PM) in nonprofit, nongovernmental educational organizations in Pakistan. The research aims to understand how employees' perceptions of PM affect key organizational variables such as work performance (WP), organizational commitment (OC), voluntary turnover intention (TI), organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), and job satisfaction (JS). A structured questionnaire was used to gather data from 164 employees of nonprofit educational organizations in Pakistan. A Likert scale questionnaire was utilized for data collection. SPSS 20 was used to do regression analysis. The results showed a significant positive correlation between employees' perceptions of PM and all dependent variables, except for voluntary turnover intention. Improvements in employees' perceptions of PM were found to enhance WP, OC, OCB, and JS while reducing voluntary TI. The study's robustness suggests that HR managers can develop improvements in PM systems that can reduce turnover rates, enhance satisfaction with work, commitment, and citizenship behavior, and increase total productivity. Future research could include comparative analyses between nonprofit and for-profit educational organizations.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern business arena, organizations are giving special importance to human resource management functions (Nizam Bin Mohd Yusof *et al.*, 2023). Human beings are considered the most important assets of organizations (Aman-Ullah *et al.*, 2022). When organizations are managing their most important and vital assets, their performance and productivity get due relevance (Gallow and Gallow, 2021). It is also said that if the employees of organizations are not giving their hundred percent output, organizations can never achieve their settled goals (Park & Choi, 2020).

Performance management PM is considered a strategic progression in which all the personnel of

organizations are reviewed in consideration of their job objectives and work contributions to the organization (Sonmez Cakir and Adiguzel, 2020). One of the most crucial aspects of human resource management is PM; its other functions are linked to rewards, retention, training, promotion, etc. Organizations can only reward, retain, train, and promote their personnel by understanding their actual performance (Okwuise and Uzoehina, 2023). Only an effective system for PM and appraisal can determine the true performance (Enaifoghe, 2024). By accomplishing individual goals, a strong PM system promotes the accomplishment of organizational goals (Erialdy, 2024). By enhancing

both individual and group performance, PM is a crucial instrument for raising an organization's level of performance (Deng *et al.*, 2024).

In today's competitive world, AI is changing the way we manage employee success by creating dynamic, data-driven tools and methods. It enhances feedback by providing actionable insights, highlighting recurring issues, and recommending tailored training and development opportunities. This proactive management approach allows for better alignment with individual strengths, weaknesses, and career goals, enhancing overall performance. Organizations can only beat their competitors if they have capable human resources (Thirunagalingam *et al.*, 2024). The retention of talented personnel can only be achieved by appropriate appraisal. A proper PM system that rectifies and differentiates between good and poor performers. PM is a helpful technique for determining the organization's areas of strength and progress (Manzoor *et al.*, 2021). The PM system's primary focus is on identifying and coordinating individual and organizational goals (Bauwens *et al.*, 2024). PM and appraisal are often interchangeable terms, but PM is a thorough approach that is usually followed continuously, while appraisal is done once a year and is often more linked with pay (Alhmod and Rjoub, 2019).

PM is an old concept and has gone through various stages. It was introduced in the early 1960s just to monitor and evaluate the overall organization's productivity (Rath and Candidate, 2018). The concept of annual confidential reports (ACRs) emerged in this era. Some employers use it with the name of the employee service record, following the same intention of measuring and modifying the behavior of employees. Both ACRs and Employee Service Records (ESRs) were directly related to the prospects of an employee in the organization (Purohit and Martineau, 2016). There was no concept of feedback in these systems, and all the records were considered confidential. This system was followed for about a decade, and then some changes emerged. The process of feedback and communication was incorporated. Employees were given feedback regarding their areas of improvement. In 1970, performance evaluations took place with the concept of ACR, and employees were allowed to list their year's accomplishments next to their

supervisors' ratings of several attributes. Some recent innovations were added to a PM system in the middle of the 1970s. The PM system was target-based, with minimal employee input into target formulation (Liu and Li, 2024).

The feedback was also constructively discussed with employees, and the concept of training and training needs assessment was also introduced via PM (Lorot, 2024). Now PM has become a continuous process, and it is still evolving. There still exist some improvements in the system, as it has been a debatable issue not only for employers but also for employees (Cosa and Torelli, 2024).

Employee performance can be evaluated in a variety of ways, including the following: management by objective; 360-degree performance appraisal; forced ranking or forced distribution; behavioral observation scales; paired comparison analysis; graphic rating scale; essay evaluation; behaviorally anchored rating scale; performance ranking method; and balanced scorecard (Werner and Bolino, 2024). All these methods are associated with some merits and demerits; still, studies are being done to further refine these methods. PM and appraisal systems are always crucial points of discussion not only for organizations but also for researchers because they help resolve different human resource management issues (Zhuang and Salleh, 2024).

It is also critical to understand how employees perceive PM systems because perception plays an important role in making things right or wrong (Padamata and Vangapandu, 2024). When it comes to accepting or rejecting ratings in the PM system, perception acts as a guiding principle (Baluch, 2017). If employees perceive the PM system as good, they will be satisfied with it, and they will have confidence in the rating (Pooja and Kumari, 2024).

Nonprofit and non-governmental groups provide a variety of services in the majority of developing nations, including Pakistan. These groups are operating in regions where the government cannot because of a lack of funding or other pressing matters (Dilshad and Bashir, 2013). Regarding employees' perceptions in profit businesses, nonprofits, and non-government sectors, PM methods have been given importance by most researchers; however, this has been disregarded. Managing the performance of workers in non-profit

and non-governmental organizations in the same way that corporate workers do is equally crucial (Thambar *et al.*, 2024).

Nonprofit and non-government organizations are commonly known as NGOs. These organizations are social organizations. They usually work for the welfare of society. The basic objectives of NGOs are different from conventional business or profit organizations. These organizations work on development issues, and they are not owned by the government (Peng, 2024).

Nonprofit and non-government sectors can be considered separate entities, keeping in mind the public and private sectors. Nonprofit and non-governmental organizations should be studied independently from public and private enterprises due to their distinct management styles, HR departments, and cultures (Rehman, 2003). Nonprofit and non-government organizations are working on so many development issues in our country, but the most important issue that is being worked on by nonprofit and non-government organizations is education (Ovcina and Arslanagic-Kalajdzic, 2024). Education is considered the backbone of society. The role of nonprofit and non-government organizations in developing countries like Pakistan, especially in education, can never be overlooked (Bokayev *et al.*, 2024).

It is also important to study these organizations as separate entities. As per my research, numerous studies have been done on PM systems, but few of them focus on nonprofit and non-government sectors (Kluijtmans and Crucke, 2024). This study aims to ascertain employees' perceptions of the nonprofit and non-government sectors' PM system and its results in Pakistan, considering the sectors' utility, benefits, and ignorance.

1.1. Research Questions:

1. What is the relationship between employee perception of the PM system and performance outcomes in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations in Pakistan?
2. How does the perception of PM affect the performance outcome in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations in Pakistan?

1.2. Research Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: WP is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: WP is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Hypothesis 2:

H₀: OC is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: OC is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Hypothesis 3:

H₀: TI is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: TI is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Hypothesis 4:

H₀: OCB is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: OCB is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Hypothesis 5:

H₀: JS is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: JS is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

Employees' Perceptions of PM and Work Performance

The relationship between employees' perceptions of PM and the work performance of the employees has a high degree of importance from the employer's

perspective. Researchers surveyed to assess important insights on the relationship between WP and the perceived transparency of PM systems have been obtained from the research (Schaerer *et al.*, 2018). According to the authors, WP is the feeling of accomplishment resulting from the fulfillment of expectations or desires (Hirschi and Spurk, 2021). It is an emotional state related to delight (Latorre-Coscolluela *et al.*, 2022). A balance between the perception of an individual of each component of their job and their beliefs about what those aspects should be leads to high WP (Kundi *et al.*, 2020). High WP depends on the level of discrepancy between what the person wants and withdraws (Abun, Nicolas, *et al.*, 2021). According to the authors' findings, the objectivity of WP systems and an employee's PM are positively correlated (Dangol, 2021). Moreover, the studies address the same variable in a different context. The author expresses that employees' perceptions of PM during their working life, seem like some employees do not know salary increments; this means that the company attaches no importance to the experience of its staff and offers no career prospects. Thus, staff begins to feel bitterness and experience desolation during the execution of their job responsibilities (Pandey and Chauhan, 2021). The study suggests that there is a cause-and-effect relationship between high WP, economic rewards (pay), material (depending on home and car service), and opportunities for professional development (Nader *et al.*, 2024). In a comparable setting, how the employees view the performance evaluation process and its impact on their dedication to the company's goals. A varied performance appraisal system is also important since it shows that senior management recognizes an employee's contribution to the workplace (Siraj and Hågen, 2023). Further another study shows that appreciation increases extrinsic motivation by confirming employees' contributions. On the other hand, recognition increases intrinsic motivation by meeting psychological needs, increasing emotional engagement, and encouraging OCB, which ultimately improves employee WP (Imran *et al.*, 2025).

Employees' Perceptions of PM and Organizational Commitment

An investigation into how employees' perceptions of PM develop about the equity of the work performance review process and how that affects their OC (Muhammad, 2022). The participants tended to have higher degrees of OC and thought the system was fair, according to the author's conclusion (Li *et al.*, 2022). Previous research indicates that an increasing disparity exists between employee aspirations and corporate goals as a result of the organization's PM system's lack of openness (Touma and Touma, 2022). This discordance becomes a source of additional costs and performance loss for the organization (Brown *et al.*, 2020). Within the company, an unbiased PM system is crucial. Employee OC and motivation were low in those firms where there were differences in the PM system. This lack of OC and motivation was even found among corporate managers (Huangpu *et al.*, 2025). According to the majority of these surveys, any sense of belonging to the organization is negatively impacted by the PM system's lack of transparency when job value remains the same (Wolor *et al.*, 2022). Previous research confirms that this phenomenon also affects the new generation of employees. The relationship with the company is distended, resulting in a loss of confidence in his speeches and practices and increasing the disengagement of employees (Cheng *et al.*, 2021). Researchers point out that companies have in recent years set up management systems and tools based on different theories of motivation to cope with the problem of low employee OC. These authors further state the tools for measuring employee performance are useful if one knows what is measured (Lee and Raschke, 2016). The concept of OC to work considers the subjectivity and desire that characterize the actual work and leaves some autonomy to employees (Kaur and Mittal, 2020). In other words, based on previous statements, it seems appropriate to consider a close and intense relationship between OC and performance appraisal systems (Bayo-Moriones and de la Torre, 2022).

Employees' Perceptions of PM and Voluntary Turnover Intention

Voluntary TI is another important variable linked to employees' perceptions of PM (Bui *et al.*, 2024). Voluntary TI is a hidden cost. Studying this cost allows us to have a better idea of its impact on productivity since it varies from one company to another (An, 2019). Employee voluntary TI reflects the scale of the movements of inputs and outputs of the service employee of a company over a given period (Al-Suraihi *et al.*, 2021). The previous studies were conducted to determine the connection between employee turnover, perceived fairness of the performance rating system, and management communication (Dixit and Bhargava, 2024). The studies addressed the finding that employee turnover, perceived fairness of the performance rating system, and management communication are related (Jha and Ray, 2021). The explanation given by the researchers that active management communication with the employees shows the organization cares about its employees. It is a demonstration of commitment to the organization's employees that gives them confidence in the fairness and objectivity of the performance review process. This explains the favorable effect on the employee's voluntary TI (Verhoeven and Madsen, 2022).

Employees' Perceptions of PM and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The theme of OCB concerning employees' perceptions of PM in recent years has generated vast research literature (Redelinghuys, 2021). The term OCB describes behaviors at work that do not fall within the role or tasks specified in the employment (Fayyad *et al.*, 2025). OCB arises from individual efforts that are not related to the duties of the employment but are important because they shape the psychological context, society, and organization (Fan *et al.*, 2023). The research also discusses the relationship between employees' perceptions of PM and OCB (Abun *et al.*, 2021). As to the authors, an employee needs to have a strong level of commitment to the company to cope with workplace harassment and other annoyances without raising the issue (Ghany, 2022). This increased attachment in turn leads to a sustained interest in the organization, which is manifested by constant and

voluntary participation in all types of events (Hodgins *et al.*, 2020). It is surprising for the authors that the empirical links between the behaviors of corporate citizenship and performance appraisal have been examined by very few researchers (Jain and Rizvi, 2018).

The performance appraisal system determines the degree of identification of a person with his/her work (Hamidi, 2023). Like all attitudes related to employment, the concept of involvement leads to an improvement in certain areas of OCB (Awan *et al.*, 2020). The perception of professional activity as a central dimension of the life of a person can cause a person to adopt OCB without the expectancy of a reward (Rahman and Karim, 2022). Finally, the authors have pointed out there is a long list of factors that lead to an exhibition of OCB at the organizational level, which is inconsistent (Rahman and Karim, 2022). Furthermore, it is imperative to have assurances that management will follow the outcomes of the PM process to recognize good performance, provide support or training to improve inadequate yield, or take appropriate action (such as assigning the employee to a different role or firing them, if necessary) when performance remains inadequate (Siraj and Hågen, 2023).

Employees' Perceptions of PM and Job Satisfaction

The prior study looked at the efficacy of PM systems and several important employee outcomes, such as work engagement, JS, and voluntary TIs. The HR systems framework, which defines effectiveness as being defined by three qualities –distinctiveness, consistency, and consensus –is the foundation upon which PM systems effectiveness is operationalized. According to the social exchange theory, workers who believe PM systems are beneficial would respond by positively changing their behavior (Kakkar *et al.*, 2020). Other studies were also conducted to examine the effect of employees' perceptions of PM on JS and OCB concerning the organization's performance appraisal system (Elrehail *et al.*, 2020).

3. Research Methodology

This study is quantitative and exploratory, particularly on nonprofit, nongovernment educational organizations in Pakistan. Quantitative

methodology has been adopted to get appropriate responses from the understudy variables. Numerous similar studies used the same methodology because it gives a clear picture of different variables that have been studied.

Primary data has been collected for quantitative analysis. A closed-ended structured questionnaire was developed and used for data collection. The research questions are divided into two sections: the first is based on the respondents' demographic data, and the second is based on the study topic focused on the relationship between the variables.

The questionnaire comprises 45 items out of which 4 items define the demographic information of respondents, while 41 items define the 6 different variables of the study. Employees' perception of PM is defined by 9 items, WP is defined by 8 items, OC is defined by 6 items, voluntary TI is defined by 4 items, OCB is defined by 7 items, and JS is also defined by 7 items. Some items have been adopted from Rajendran, 2008.

A structured questionnaire was used to gather data from 164 employees. A Likert scale questionnaire was utilized for data collection. SPSS 20 was used to do regression analysis. A pre-test was conducted on

10 respondents from a nonprofit and non-government education organization to check the validity of the instrument. The pre-test helped rephrase the questions and make them easier and more understandable. The respondents gave a few suggestions regarding the instruments, which were taken into consideration. The questionnaire was designed in an online and printable version.

A reliability test is also conducted to check the reliability of items defining a single variable. The results of the test ensure the reliability of the instrument. The survey method was adopted for data collection, and questionnaires were sent to different nonprofit and non-government educational organizations as well as individuals working in different nonprofit and non-government educational organizations.

A correlation analysis is used in research to demonstrate the relationship and strength between two variables. Furthermore, Regression analysis is also used to determine and examine the relationship between one or more independent and dependent variables. This approach demonstrates if a relationship exists and how strong it is.

3.1. Theoretical Framework

Research Findings

Statistical tools were applied to the data collected to test the hypothesis of the research. Following are the findings of the study.

3.2. Reliability Statistics

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Perception of PM	0.918	9
WP	0.788	8
OC	0.878	6
TI	0.906	4
OCB	0.689	7
JS	0.886	7

Table 4.1 above shows the reliability statistics of all the variables in the study. The alpha coefficient value for all the mentioned items defining a single variable is greater than 0.65. It shows high internal consistency and reliability of instrument.

3.3. Correlation Analysis

Table 4.2
Correlations

	WP	OC	TI	OCB	JS
Employees' perception of PM	.290	.661	-.522	.272	.749
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	164	164	164	164

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Table 4.2 above is a correlation matrix that shows the relationship of variables examined in the study. It can be argued that the relationship between employees' perception of PM with WP, OC, voluntary TI, OCB, and JS is a statistically significant correlation as the value of Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.000 is less than 0.05. If we comment on the intensity of the relationship among these variables, then except voluntary TI, all the variables have a positive sign with a Pearson correlation result (can be seen in the table above), which shows that voluntary TI is negatively correlated with employees' perception of PM while other variables, i.e., WP, OC, OCB, and JS, are positively correlated.

There exists a strong positive correlation between employees' perception of PM and JS, as the Pearson correlation result is 0.749, which is close to 1. A strong positive correlation also exists between employees' perception of PM and OC because of the Pearson correlation of approximately 0.7, which is

closer to 1, while a weak positive correlation exists between employees' perception of PM with WP and OCB as the results are 0.29 and 0.27, closer to zero. The only moderately negative correlation exists between employees' perception of PM and voluntary TI, as the Pearson correlation is -0.522, which is neither closer to zero nor one.

3.4. Regression Analysis

A regression model has been run to further check the hypothesis and independent variable as predictors of the dependent variable.

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: WP is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: WP is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Table 4.3

Independent Variable	Coefficient	T	Sig
Constant	3.409	20.085	.000
Perception of PM	.177	3.862	.000
R ²	0.084		

Dependent Variable: WP

Table 4.3 shows the result of a regression model. One unit increase in employees' perception of PM will increase WP by 0.177 units. The relation between the independent variable (employees' perception of PM) and dependent variable (WP) is statistically significant at a 1% significance level, which means that employees' perception of PM is a useful predictor of WP. This model explains an 8.4%

variation in the dependent variable. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2:

H₀: OC is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: OC is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Table 4.4

Independent Variable	Coefficient	T	Sig
Constant	1.496	6.903	.000
Perception of PM	.655	11.218	.000
R ²	.437		

Dependent Variable: OC

Table 4.4 shows the result of a regression model. One unit increase in employees' perception of PM will increase OC by 0.655 units. The relation between the independent variable (employees' perception of PM) and dependent variable (OC) is statistically significant at a 1% significance level, which means that employees' perception of PM is a useful predictor of OC. This model explains a 43.7% variation in the dependent variable. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 3:

H₀: The voluntary TI is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

H_a: The voluntary TI is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Table 4.5

Independent Variable	Coefficient	T	Sig
Constant	5.566	15.348	.000
Perception of PM	-.761	-7.784	.000
R ²	.272		

Dependent Variable: voluntary TI

Table 4.5 shows the result of a regression model. One unit increase in employees' perception of PM will decrease voluntary TI by 0.761 units. The relation between the independent variable (employees' perception of PM) and dependent variable (voluntary TI) is statistically significant at a 1% significance level, which means that employees' perception of PM is a useful predictor of voluntary TI. This model explains a 27.2% variation in the

dependent variable. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 4:

H₀: OCB is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.
 H_a: OCB is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Table 4.6

Independent Variable	Coefficient	T	Sig
Constant	2.952	14.873	.000
Perception of PM	.193	3.602	.000
R ²	.074		

Dependent Variable: OCB

Table 4.6 shows the result of a regression model. One unit increase in employees' perception of PM will increase WP by 0.193 units. The relation between the independent variable (employees' perception of PM) and the dependent variable (OCB) is statistically significant at a 1% significance level, which means that employees' perception of PM is a useful predictor of OCB. This model explains a 7.4% variation in the dependent variable. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 5:

H₀: JS is not determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.
 H_a: JS is determined by the employees' perception of the PM system in nonprofit and non-government educational organizations of Pakistan.

Table 4.7

Independent Variable	Coefficient	T	Sig
Constant	.637	3.120	.000
Perception of PM	.791	14.376	.000
R ²	.561		

Dependent Variable: JS

Table 4.7 shows the result of a regression model. One unit increase in employees' perception of PM will increase JS by 0.791 units. The relation between the independent variable (employees' perception of PM) and dependent variable (JS) is statistically significant at a 1% significance level, which means that employees' perception of PM is a useful predictor of JS. This model explains the 56.1% variation in the dependent variable. Based on these findings, the null hypothesis is rejected.

4. Discussion

The purpose of the study was to investigate the relationships between employee perceptions of PM and its outcomes, such as WP, OC, voluntary TI, OCB, and JS in nonprofit, nongovernmental educational organizations in Pakistan. The findings show that voluntary TI is negatively correlated with employee perceptions of PM, whereas WP, OC, OCB, and JS are positively correlated. Previous research has also demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between WP and employees' perceptions of their performance appraisals (Bušatlić

and Musić-Kilic Sarajevo, 2018). Additionally, research has indicated a positive and significant relationship between employees' perceptions of PM and OC, OCB, and JS (Miah and Talukder, 2012; Hidayah and Harnoto, 2018). Numerous research studies revealed a correlation between the variables concerning the negative relationship between employees' perceptions of PM and voluntary TI (Kakkar *et al.*, 2020).

By contributing more empirical evidence to the substantial amount of research on the relevant subject, this study enhances the understanding of the significance of employees' perceptions of PM in nonprofit, nongovernmental educational organizations in Pakistan. Organizations should take extra care while implementing PM systems to motivate employees to work hard to achieve the aims and objectives of the organization. Improved WP, OC, OCB, JS, and reduced voluntary TI are difficult to expect when employees are unaware of what's expected of themselves. In today's competitive world, the way we can manage the employees is by creating a dynamic environment. It enhances employee feedback by providing training and development opportunities. This proactive management approach allows for better alignment with individual strengths, weaknesses, and career goals, enhancing overall performance. Organizations can only beat their competitors if they have capable human resources. All dependent variables had a positive association with employees' evaluations of the PM system, except for voluntary TI. One result is that increasing the independent variable has a beneficial impact on all of the dependent variables. After a thorough examination, all of the null hypotheses have been rejected based on the regression model's findings.

5. Conclusion

The effectiveness of nonprofit, nongovernmental educational organizations in Pakistan is significantly influenced by their human resource management strategies. Therefore, the results of PM systems may benefit organizations not only in rewarding or appraising employees but also in increasing WP, OC, OCB, and JS, while decreasing voluntary TI. Performance management was studied in this research, and the analysis of various variables and their impact on the perception of PM systems shows

a positive correlation with WP, OC, OCB, and JS while a negative correlation with voluntary TI.

The consequence of the study concluded that all the dependent variables are not only correlated with the independent variable but also have meaningful relationships. Improvement in employees' perception will lead to improvement in the dependent variable (WP, OC, TI, OCB, and JS).

5.1. Recommendations

This study provides potentially new information pathways for academics, students, and human resource managers in Pakistan's nonprofit, nongovernmental educational organizations. Since nothing is perfect, it becomes necessary to get past the study's constraints as well. Here are some recommendations that ought to be considered.

a. Based on the analysis, this study recommends the policymaker inculcate such policies for PM systems that appreciate positivity for the system and build good perception among employees.

b. The study found that perception is important, therefore companies should make their PM system transparent and use appropriate feedback and communication to allow employees to voice any concerns they might possess.

c. Organizations should establish an appeal system for employees if they find any discrimination regarding their PM.

d. PM should not only give feedback on an annual basis, but employees should also be informed of their performance throughout the year so that they may have better performance and confidence in the system being practiced.

e. Further research is required to ascertain other possible consequences of employees' perceptions of PM systems. It would be beneficial to undertake a study that includes additional variables, such as work-life conflicts, employee motivation, and retention.

f. The study merely discusses how employees perceive PM systems; it does not inquire into the factors that influence their opinions. Research on the factors influencing employees' opinions of PM systems is necessary.

g. Organizations should make sure that managers and subordinates understand the PM system and objectives so that they can work

accordingly. Proper dissemination should be established. Every employee should know why performance is being evaluated.

h. Since this study solely includes data from employees and ignores employer narratives, more research is required that takes employers' points of view into account.

i. Employees have identified WP, thus there may have been some factual tampering. It is possible to research to verify this variable from the perspectives of employers and employees.

j. Organizations can involve employees in setting performance targets so that they will feel ownership and they will know the criteria of evaluation. Perception can be enhanced by adopting such ways.

5.2. Suggestion /Future areas of research

During this study, some future areas can be explored. The following areas have the potential to direct the research.

a. A study can be conducted between nonprofit nongovernment educational organizations and nonprofit nongovernment disaster management organizations.

b. To further differentiate the PM practices of nonprofit, nongovernment educational organizations from private organizations. A comparative analysis can be conducted.

c. Motivation, retention, and work-life conflict can be conducted by selecting other variables.

d. Since this study is being carried out in Pakistan, it is possible to compare the PM practices of some other nations that fall under the umbrella of nonprofit, nongovernmental educational institutions.

Within the same industry, research on factors influencing employees' opinions of PM systems might be conducted.

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